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A Study on the Lyrical and Musical Elements of Two Bengali Folk songs: Baul and Bhawaiya- An Analysis

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Abstract

The article focusses on the lyrical and musical elements of two bengali folk songs of Baul and Bhawaiya genre to observe the factors that work as catalysts to form the individual characteristics of the art pieces. The melodious nature of 'Baul' and 'Bhawaiya' songs has their purpose to do more than entertaining their audiences. The costume and attires of a 'Baul', perhaps, communicate detachment from fast moving modern life or just being different. 'Bhawaiya' inter-mingles into regular routine of life and quest for meaning; and may express desire to escape from that routine towards different. The study analyses the lyrical content of both the songs to understand the factors that give the songs, in relation to their genres, their self-narrating nature of rationale of their formation.

Keywords : Bengali Folk Songs, Baul, Bhatiyali, Bhawaiya, Ethnomusicology

Research Methodology: *The two songs are chosen by simple random sampling method. The elements of songs such as the language and native dialectical identity, the background context to form the genre and the selected songs, the musical elements such as the notations, structure, rhythm, tempo and mood, instruments, the overall tunes- all are critically analyzed to understand the elements that depict the cultural identity and rationale behind the formation of the songs.*

Introduction

The Baul songs of Bengal carry esoteric and philosophical meaning of life along with the dialectical identity and musical value. The Baul songs narrate different range of topics from devotion and surrender to highest master, to the parallel existence of reality, to the connection between human sexual practices and spirituality. The true messages are hidden and presented to the audience metaphorically so that they remain "inaccessible to the uninitiated audience" (Krakauer 2015:12). The musical elements help the Baul performance remain engaging for the audience. On the other hand, the Bhawaiya songs deal with the day-to-day activities of cattle herders, and their inner most yearnings for their separated lovers. The metaphors of the songs can be interpreted two-folds- philosophic and

romantic, or both. The musical attributes Bhawaiya songs are simpler than Baul songs as the use of instruments and musical nuances are less.

Study Area

- i. Lyrical Analysis of the Baul song 'Oh Majhi re' (song 1):

The English translation of the song¹ goes-
Oh, dear Boatman,

why don't you ply your paddle?

How can you waste your days sitting idle

When you have this beautiful sail,

Oh boatman!

In every layer of wind,

You ply your paddle intensely.

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Or, when the breath flow in reverse,
You will lose away (all).
The broken boat of Bhaba pagla,
Has no rope to bind the boat,
So, the water gets stagnant at the bottom,
How to sail!

The song has many rhetorical uses of simple words of regular practice. The metaphorical translation of the song can be interpreted as below:

Oh human, why don't you live your life passionately,

See how wonderful opportunity of living life you have gotten.

Why do you waste your time sitting idle?

Oh human!

In every moment, you live your life with mindfulness and passion.

Otherwise, you may lose all opportunity of life

When you breath last.

The imperfect/unmindful life of human

Has no control over the manifestations of the events of life.

So, the unwanted setbacks block the vision for life,

And thus, make the journey of life difficult.

Oh human!

Focusing on the uses of the metaphor in the song, the lyrics of the song uses simple words of daily use poetically (Paddle, sail, sitting idle, plying boat, layers of mind, rope to bind, the water etc.) and attempts to remind the 'ultimate' duty of human life. This is how the lyrics becomes easily graspable, although the underlying meaning takes to different area of perception. The use of the word 'boat' signifies the 'body' (or life) and the 'boatman' is the soul (or human) who is the

decider to which way and how the life should be directed; whereas, the river is the 'field of scope' which is to be utilized attentively; and when the journey ends, one might not get the scope to live the same journey once again. The addressing is informal, but not intimate; as the lyrics conveys the meaning allegorically and not directly.

ii. Background context of the genre in relation to the song:

The geographical region of (un/divided) Bengal is surrounded by waterbodies with some geo-politically significant rivers which witnessed pre and post partition transitions of livelihood marked by infamous Bengal Partition 1905 as "many of the partition narratives help construct emotional relationships with rivers which assume particular significance during the trauma of partition" (Raychaudhuri, 2019:146). The mass social trauma of partition⁴ has given in contribution of many philosophical literary and musical works reflected in different genres of folk songs especially 'Bhatiyali' as River Ganges/Padma carries the memory of the tension and trauma of separation from motherland and un/re-settlement of the people of 1950s Bengal. (Ranjan, 2021:13)

There have been many literary works⁵ based on the lives of boatmen and life around rivers in Bengali literature. The song literally suggests of a boatman who sits idle and is reluctant to paddle the boat. The daily life of a boatman is monotonous and this gives scope for artistic explorations and creations. The philosophical aspect of idle life of a boatman is metaphorically depicted in the lyrics.

iii. The Musical analysis of song 1 "Oh Majhi Re":

Some of the musical phrases in the song can be identified as similar to Raga Jhinjhoti. There are also phrases that can be identified as similar to Raga khamaj.

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In the prelude, the introductory melody starts with the flute along with synth-base chords and mandolin as fillers for the gaps. In the Body, the Tabla starts with a 'tihayi' as the rhythmic intro in Line 1 and continues accompanying by changing patterns of strokes to complement the melodic poetry by the vocals. The use of violin is occasional. The chords by the synth pad are maintained throughout. The first interlude has melody pieces of violin, flute and mandolin respectively. In the second interlude, flute and mandolin is played where flute dominates. In the ending tail, the flute is played as complementary accompaniment along with the vocal.

The style of singing is open throat. The pronunciations of words are soft and with casual articulation of some words which sustains the dialectical impression over the melodic performance. The artist has a specific language accent (nasal articulation and loud production) that makes the performance more like a melodic conversation. The song is set in pitch F.

Medium fast pace rhythm with a Jhinjhoti Raga melody is combination that depicts the dual nature of the mood as the lyrics. Jhinjhoti is a 'Shringaar Rasa' Raga depicts romance or sadness with the fast pace brings a satirical comic mood.

The rhythm follows the pattern of beat that compliments the temperament of the melody. As it initiates, the song introduces the melody without rhythm and gradually holds the words along with the rhythm. It is a common system in Indian music where the melody is introduced without rhythm before starting the rendition full-fledged.

The use of synthesizer to produce instrumental melody and the sound of 'Dotara' compliments the imagery of water cascade which create an animated set of melody in the background overall.

iv. Lyrical Analysis of the Bhawaiya song "Fande poriya" (song 2):

The English translation of the song 'Faande poriya boga kaande' is given below:

A 'Boga' (male egret) cries falling in the trap ||
The trapper sets the trap with 'puti' fish, oh brother
The foolish egret, out of greed, falls into the trap ||
The egret, falling into the trap
pulls the yellow, rusty iron fibers ||
The egret falls in trap and cries in despair
Oh, tremendous fate! The companion is leaving ||
A flying 'chakora' bird sideways informs the 'Bogi' (the female egret)
'Your boga is trapped by the side of the Dolla (Dhorola) river' ||
Hearing so, 'Bogi' spreads her two wings,
Flies towards the river and meets 'Boga' |
Seeing Boga, Bogi cries
Seeing Bogi, Boga cries ||

There are colloquially used words that present the identity of the native dialect in the song. There are many rhetorical uses of words in the song to generate metaphorical meaning. However, the metaphors of the lyrics can be seen with two perspectives. One, with the hard reality of complex relationships that exists in the material world where the choice of life decisions is bound by consequences, although taken by free will. Two, choosing to experience life in the 'material' world costs separation from the realization of the cosmic self of being as the 'material' world is the 'trap' of worldly pleasures which are set as choices of freewill but bound by life consequences.

The egret metaphorically signifies the men and women in general who, in order to experience worldly pleasures which are signified by the small 'puti fish', choose the directions of lives. The 'trapper' (faandi) may be the fate or

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God or the designer of the material world.

- v. Background context of the genre in relation to the song:

The popular impression of the term 'Bhawaiya' among its practitioners and audience is a "form of plaintive ballads that speak of love and loss and endless longing within a women's heart" (Datta, 2019). The term comes from 'bhab' meaning 'inner feeling'. The Bhawaiya songs are mostly composed by men, however, the lyrics predominantly narrates and expresses the tale of separation or yearning for the companion of a woman. Therefore, the "expressions of female desire and grief for her absent male lover can be construed as the wishful dreams of lonely men leading harsh, solitary lives" (Datta, 2019).

The melodious identity of Bhawaiya are the prolonged lines and vocal breaks in between elongated notes. The vocal breaks are believed to have come into practice after singing while the journey through the uneven roads by the 'Garowals' (cart drivers) in the bullock carts. "It is said that the baidiyas, the cattle herders and cart drivers would sit down at the end of a hard day and compose such songs on their dotaras" (Datta, 2019) with the hope that the longing they have for their women of love interests, long for them as well with equal intensity.

- vi. The Musical analysis of the song 'Faande Poriya' (song 2):

There are two instruments accompanying with the melody and one for the rhythm. The flute and the dotara are played to follow as the same melody as the vocal parts. Also, the elongated notes are accompanied by the base notes by the dotara as fillers. The khartal is giving rhythm on the first units of every four-unit division of bar. In the places where melodic tension is given in elongated notes, the khartal beats are doubled.

There is a short prelude by the dotara.

As the prelude piece of dotara ends, the flute is holding the melody by fading in and both the instruments continues accompanying in throughout the song till the end.

The instruments follow the vocal that is sung predominantly without leaving much scope or need for fillers. The volume of the instruments is as low as they give the same melody to support the vocal parts. The khartal, although is giving the rhythm base, however, it is also giving the register melody note that is well audible.

The song has a prelude of four cycles of six counts beats. The lines are not repeated except the first that is also repeated only after finishing each stanza. The song has no interlude and instrumental tail.

There are phrases of Raga Bilawal in the song. However, the repeated use of komal Ni, breaks the pattern of Bilawal raga. Although all the notes used in the song are similar like that of Raga Khamaj, the movement of the melody does not follow either of the patterns of both the raga. So, the melody of the song is a mixed melody adjacent to raga Bilawal and Khamaj.

Discussion :

There is a relevance of Baul and Bhatiyali^{2,6} (two folk genres) in the same song as observed in the analysis of song1. The Baul compositions are concerned with self-realisation merging divine realization. Bhatiyali songs (sung by Boatmen sailing downstream sometimes express the grief of separation from beloved or dear ones; and in most cases Bhatiyali songs use the phenomenon of the flow of the river and the boat to denote the imagery of the spiritual nature and urge for spiritual meaning of human life. However, the use of the metaphor of river and boat was greatly used during late 18th- early 19th century in Baul compositions (Mukharji, 2009:171). Since centuries, the water ways of deltaic Bengal (East and West) were the

prominent root to economy and livelihood, the metaphors of river and river related phenomenon occupy a great space of the folk literature of the rural imagination of this region.

As 'Bhawaiya' songs mostly narrate the unfulfilled desire of love and yearning between men and women, the current song may portray the story of separation⁷ of two lovers among one fall prey to momentary pleasures that caused permanent or long-term separation between them. There is a common context between 'Bhawaiya' and River Dhorola⁸. As the native dialect of northern West Bengal and north-western Bangladesh are same and similar, 'Bhawaiya', a prominent genre of Bengali folk songs, emerged and popularized in this geo-cultural region since "16th century during the reign of Raja Biswa Sinha of Kooch Bihar" (Datta, 2019).

Conclusion :

The dialects of both the songs carry the simplicity of expressing the emotions and meaning to penetrate into the relevant society. The songs evolve from the subculture that appears partially distinctive from each other. The universal nature of folk songs narrating the mundane human life is prominently present with hints of universal mysteries of life.

The musical nature of song 1 is much more orchestrated as it involves modern production techniques; however, the basic composition follows the simple structure of general Baul songs. The composition of the song 2 is even simpler than song 1, and bases on refrains of notations in the stanzas. This style of musical composition helps the song to be free from compositional distraction as the lyrics is made in the style of a particular story-telling or musical ballad. The songs cannot be bound to any certain Indian classical Raga as the musical compositions enjoy liberty of native tunes similar

to the scale of Khamaj Raga. The use of 'Dotara'⁹ is prominent in the Bhawaiya song, however, the Baul song also has melody parts in preludes and interludes which give both the songs their due identity of the genres belonging to Bengali folk tunes.

The metaphors of river and river related phenomenon depict the nostalgia of geographic land and events of life related to it. The metaphors of fish, egret, separation, fish-net, boat, boat man etc. depict the deep understanding and reflection of life phenomenon which is the universal purpose and rationale behind any folk genre. Along with this, the esoteric nature of both the songs and the genres represents the spiritual nature of human that urge to find philosophical meaning of different events of life.

As observed in the study, because of the connection between the song-writer and the region of Bengal, divided and undivided; the Baul and Bhatiyali elements are intermixed in song 1. This is an example of circumstance where the amalgamation of art forms take place after un/re-settlement of communities from one region to another.

Notes :

1. The song 'Oh Majhi re' is sung by Bipad Taran Das Baul. The lyrics and musical composition are done by 'Bhaba Pagla' (pseudonym).
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0OocXcyiXgk>
(last accessed on 05/04/23)
2. The composer of the song1, Bhaba pagla was a folk music writer, composer and mystic born in Eastern region of Bengal, now Bangladesh. As the mysticism is the core attribute of the folk imagination of Bengal, the literal representations of the spiritual revelations of Bhaba Pagla are no exception. However, as during later part of life, after the partition of India and Bangladesh, Bhaba came to this West Bengal of India at Kalna of Burdwan district (Western Bengal, now India) the folk songs of him carries the dual nature of Baul and Bhatiyali music. The current song starts with the rhythmless introductory tune illustration with the words "oh Majhi" (Oh Boatman) which is a

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key character of Bhatiyali songs, however, the suggestive nature of the lyrics and the use of pseudonym are characters of Baul songs. In regard to this, the quote from the book "Baul songs of Bengal" of Sanat Kumar Bose suggesting, "the tunes in eastern districts of Bengal have semblances of Bhatiyali of the northern region of 'Bhawaiya'. Those of western parts are slightly different and usually very lengthy" (Bose, 1967:54) may bring clarity to understand the nature of this song.

<http://www.bhabapaglaashram.org/> (website of Bhaba pagla, last accessed on 05/04/23)

3. The song 'Faande poriya boga kaande' was first recorded in 1939 under the record label: HMV N17332. The lyrics and composition are done by Abbas Uddin Ahmed and also sung by himself. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bSHCQFRRmSs> (last accessed on 05/04/23)
4. Additional read: Biswas, A. K. (1995). Paradox of Anti-Partition Agitation and Swadeshi Movement in Bengal (1905). *Social Scientist*, 23(4/6), 38-57. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3520214>
5. The folk songs used in Ritwik Ghatak's film "Titas ekti Nadir Naam" can be referred. Also read: SARKAR, B. (2009). CODA: The Critical Enchantment of Mourning. In *Mourning the Nation: Indian Cinema in the Wake of Partition*, 200-209, 299-304. Duke University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv11sms6r.12>
6. Additional read: Lorea, C. E. (2015). If people get to know me, I'll become cow-dung: Pu?pik?: Tracing Ancient India Through Texts and Traditions, 132-160. <https://doi.org/10.2307/J.CTVH1DNZS.10>
7. Additional read: An essay on folk music of Bengal with detailed description on "Bhawaiya" by Azarul Muradh https://www.academia.edu/9216428/Folk_Music_of_Bengal
8. Dharala river is a tributary of Brahmaputra that flows

through Assam, India. The river from its source covers three countries of sub-Himalayan belt. The states the river flows through are Sikkim and West Bengal of India, Rangpur of Bangladesh and Para of Bhutan. http://en.banglapedia.org/index.php?title=Dharla_River

9. A point to note here is that 'Ektara' is played by the 'Bauls' of Western part of West Bengal like Bankura, Birbhum, Purulia districts. 'Dotara' (two string plucking Instrument) and 'Sarinda' (Folk bow Instrument) are practiced and played mostly by the 'Bauls' of Northern parts of West Bengal like Dinajpur, Malda districts etc.

References :

- Bose, S. K. (1967). *Baul songs of Bengal, Folkmusic and Folklore, An Anthology*, Vol.1, 54
- Datta, S. (2019). *The Solitude of Love: Nature, Culture and Womanhood in Bhawaiya Songs*, <https://www.sahapedia.org/solitude-love-nature-culture-and-womanhood-Bhawaiya-songs-0> (article link last accessed on 05/01/23)
- Krakauer, B. (2015). The Ennobling of a "Folk Tradition" and the Disempowerment of the Performers: Celebrations and Appropriations of B?ul-Fakir Identity in West Bengal. *Ethnomusicology*, 59(3), 355-379,12
- Mukharji, Manjita (2009). *Reading the metaphors in Baul songs: Some reflections on the social history of rural colonial Bengal*. PhD thesis. SOAS University of London,171
- Ranjan, A. (2021). Rivers and canals as "other factors" in the partition of India. *Water History*, 1-17 DOI:10.1007/s12685-021-00286-4
- Raychaudhuri, A. (2019). "I still dream of the Padma": Changing Riverscapes of Partition, Narrating South Asian Partition: Oral History, Literature, Cinema. Oxford University Press, C6,146 DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190249748.003.0007>